

Cohesion and Coherence in the Registers of Medicine, Religion and Law

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Abstract

Language, a means of communication that is peculiar to humans, is a phenomenon that has attracted the attention of various disciplines: Linguistics, Sociology, Anthropology and Psychology among others. Within Linguistics, various approaches have been adopted to the study of language. One of such approaches is semantics. Semantics in linguistic analysis is a technical term used to refer to the study of meaning. The concepts of Cohesion and Coherence have a lot to do with the meaning of conversation and texts in relation to issues of context of situation, linguistic setting, linguistic environment and linguistic relationship both of which are very useful in analyzing discourses in English Language. This paper, therefore, examined the concepts of Cohesion and Coherence in the registers of medicine, religion and law with a view to pointing out their relevance to meaning. Halliday and Matthiessen's Systemic Functional Grammar Theory served as the theoretical framework. Existing studies have not examined the two concepts together in a paper as the present study has done. The study adopted the purposive sampling technique in collecting the data. The selected data are in three professions of medicine, religion and law. The choice of these three areas was informed by their significant use of the concepts of cohesion and coherence. Each of the data was analyzed qualitatively. Findings in the study show the centrality of these concepts to meaning-making in the mentioned fields. Further finding shows the relationship between the use of language and contextual situation. The paper recommended that Language use in a particular field should be explicated in terms of its cohesive devices and coherence means. The paper also recommended that at the tertiary level of education, departments should

incorporate courses on the use of language in their fields into their syllabi. The contents of such courses should include Cohesion and Coherence in linguistic study.

Keywords: Language, Communication, Meaning, Registers, Situational Context

1. Introduction

The relevance of English Language to the educational advancement of countries all over the world where it is used as an official language is quite remarkable. The language is studied as a separate discipline in tertiary institutions; English language is a core subject that all students in the secondary schools offer and all classes in the Primary schools study it as a subject. For users of English as a foreign language or second language, learning of vocabulary has always been a daunting issue. With the expansion of the size of vocabulary, problems arise as regards the proper use of words in context. For example, users of English Language mainly concern themselves with how to increase the number of words they can remember at the expense of the depth of their understanding of the words. How to dig deep into the depth of these words is indeed a major problem facing them. The concepts of cohesion and coherence are important aspects of truly knowing words in English language. This paper therefore examines these linguistic concepts, enquires into their relevance to meaning and finally provides some suggestions for their learning.

2. Semantics and meaning

Within linguistics, various approaches have been adopted to the study of language. One of such approaches is semantics. Indeed, semantics is a sub-discipline of linguistics which focuses on the study of meaning. It shows meaning as an element of language and how it is constructed by language as well as interpreted and negotiated by listeners of language. Wood (2011) says that semantics is closely linked with another sub-discipline of linguistics, pragmatics which is also, broadly speaking, the study of meaning.

Meaning has been given different definitions. Kempson (1977) sees meaning as the idea that the word brings forth in the speaker or the hearer's mind. It is a mentalistic form of theory

which locates the meaning of a word in the head of the speaker or hearer. Adeoye (2010:04) defines meaning as the relationship between the word and the object to which it refers. Zradkovic (2017) sees meaning in the context in which it is used. For Nordquist (2018), meaning is the message conveyed by words, sentences and symbol in a context.

Semantics as a study uses meaning as an extension (Zradkovic, 2017; Nordquist, 2018). That is the thing in the world that the word / phrase evokes. The study of semantics looks at how meaning works in a language and because of this, it often uses native speaker intuition about the meaning of words and phrases to base research on. It looks at the relationship in language and looks at how meanings are created which is an important part of understanding how language works as a whole. Adeyinka (2012) says that semantics is also informed by other sub disciplines of linguistics, such as morphology, as understanding the words themselves is integral to the study of their meaning. It is also related to syntax which researchers in semantics use extensively to reveal how meaning is created in language.

3. Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG) Theory as developed by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014). The theory is traceable to J.R. Firth who lived between 1890 and 1960. M.A.K Halliday, however, developed the linguistic model in the late 1950s and early 1960 (Halliday, 1978, 1985; Oha, 1993; Osisanwo, 2005). The SFG came as a form of grammar in reaction to Structural Grammar (SG) and Transformational Generative Grammar (TGG). It came into existence because of the claim by SG pursued in TGG that meaning had no place in grammar.

Osisanwo (2005:33) says that language must be studied with real social context, and language text must be attributed to participants in some context of situation. Adeoye (2014:03) supports this view, as he cited mead's (n.d) explanation that meaning is created in the process of role taking which involves shifting back and forth between imagination and observation. Odebunmi (2001:25) is of the view that context is the spine of meaning. It is in fact, extremely difficult to proceed with any reasonable search for meaning without considering contextual pressure on word usage. The SFG, as a linguistic theory, reflects the social use to which language is put. Olupe (2019:34) says the basic principle of SFG is to consider language as a social behavior which only becomes meaningful when used in context.

4. Methodology

This study adopts the purposive sampling technique in collecting the data. The study purposively selected data in three professions / careers of Law, Medicine and Religion. The choice of these three areas was informed by their significant use of the concepts of cohesion and coherence. The data were sourced through the audio-visual mode as recorded by the mass media in the news and online, all of which were transcribed for analysis purpose. The data are excerpts of an interview with Dr. Stella Immanuel by Joel Eisenbaum of KPRC Radio Station in Houston, United States of America on her views on the issue of COVID 19 on the 30th July, 2020 (Medicine): excerpts from texts of doctor-doctor and doctor-patient interaction in 93 days (a 2016 movie on Ebola Prevention in Lagos, Nigeria) (Medicine): excerpts from “Perfect Blessings”, a Christian sermon delivered by Pastor Enoch Adeboye of the Redeem Christian Church of God during the RCCG July, 2021 Holy Ghost Service (Religion) and excerpts from “Miracles don’t just happen”, a Christian sermon delivered by Pastor Tunde Bakare of the Latter Rain Assembly on the 21st March, 2021 (Religion). Others are excerpts of an Interview with Barrister Tolu Babayele by Channel’s Television Reporters on 28th May, 2016 on the extradition case against Late Mr. Buruji Kashamu by the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) in Nigeria (Law) and excerpts from the Judgement of the Supreme Court of Nigeria on a Presidential Election Matter between the Presidential candidate of the People’s Democratic Party, Alhaji Atiku Abubakar and the Presidential candidate of the All Progressive Congress (APC), who is also the incumbent Nigerian leader, President Muhammadu Buhari. The judgement was delivered on the 30th October, 2019 (Law)

5. Cohesion and Coherence

5.1 Cohesion

The meaning of cohesion is sticking together. Trappex-Lomax (2000) while quoting Halliday and Hassan (1976) says that cohesion refers to the range of possibilities for linking something with what had gone before. Halliday and Hassan (1976) say that cohesion occurs where the interpretation of some elements in a text is dependent on that of another. Osisanwo (2008) describes cohesion as a linguistic means by which a text functions as a single unit. Ekeoha (2009) citing Halliday and Hassan (2001) observes that the primary determinant of whether a

set of sentences do or do not constitute a text depends on cohesive relationship within and between the sentences which creates texture and this is what distinguishes it from something that is not a text. The texture is provided by the cohesive relation.

For example, where the interpretation of some elements in the discourse is dependent on that of another and the one presupposes the other in the sense that it cannot be effectively decoded except by recourse to it, cohesive relationships within a text are set up. The aforesaid can be illustrated thus:

- i) Victoria left the office early, yesterday.
- ii) Victoria's mother was ill at home.

(Osisanwo, 2008: p28)

For the purpose of cohesion, the two sentences can be written thus. Victoria left the office early yesterday because her mother was ill at home. Onadeko (2000) says that cohesion can be seen as residing in the semantic and grammatical properties of the language. He further states that cohesion addresses itself to the question of how sentences are tied up together to form a limited text. Adeoye (2014) citing Onadeko (2000) avers that cohesion exists at two levels in the analysis of discourse in English language. They are intraturn and interturn. Intraturn cohesion is what Halliday and Hassan (2001) and Nordquist (2018) describe as inter-sentence and cohesion. It involves the nature of cohesive elements i.e. whether they are semantic or syntactic in their direction. i.e. whether they point to what precedes (anaphoric) or follows (cataphoric) them in terms of number of sentences intervening between the cohesive item and the element to which it refers. These can be illustrated thus:

iii) Wash the plates very well. Put them in the kitchen cabinet (intraturn, anaphoric cohesion)

iv) This is what we are saying. Child abuse is dangerous (intraturn, cataphoric cohesion)

Interturn cohesion exists at the interpersonal level of discourse. There should be cohesion in what interactants say. For example:

v) Speaker A: Which local Government do you come from?

Speaker B: Ijebu-North

Speaker A: What did you call it?

The above illustration implies that cohesion does not exist in monologue alone but also occurs in interpersonal talk.

(Halliday & Hassan, 1989; Onadeko, 2000; Adeyinka, 2012; Nordquist, 2018) have identified a number of cohesive ties. They include Reference, conjunction, substitution, Ellipsis and lexical cohesion.

Reference: This has to do with looking elsewhere for the interpretation of items which Brown and Yule (1985) refer to as co-reference form. Reference could be exophoric or endophoric. Exophoric is where its interpretation lies outside the text. Exophoric cohesion can be illustrated thus:

vi) One year ago, I was privileged to stand before you, to take the oath of office as President of our dear country (former President Goodluck Jonathan, 2012)

In the above statement, the use of One year ago is a cohesive device which refers to the day the President was sworn into office. This is a time / period outside the context of the speech but its significance affects the speech. The President would not be delivering the speech as President without reference to that day.

Reference is endophoric where its interpretation lies within the text and forms cohesive ties within the text. The endophoric relations are also divided into two – anaphoric reference which refers backward in the text and cataphoric which refers forward in the text. For example:

vii) Several people approached. They seemed to get angry (anaphoric)

viii) She is here. The girl that was harassed (cataphoric)

Conjunction: This cohesive device indicates the nature of meaning relations between clauses and sentences. In this cohesive device, longer discourse units are often used. Adeyinka (2012) puts the meaning relation thus:

(a) Additive links (and, moreover, furthermore). The people had a lot of problems. Moreover, their creditors did not give them any breathing space.

(b) Temporal links (then, after, later on, subsequently) e.g. I carried out the instruction. Then I sat down waiting for my boss.

(c) Adversative links (but, although, nevertheless, even so) e.g. We saw her on the field. Nevertheless he was not doing anything.

(d) Causal links (so, therefore, as a result, in consequence) e.g. As a result of our action, the man paid his debt.

(e) Continuatives (well, anyway) e.g. We have tried our best. Well, we have to continue.

Substitution: This cohesive device entails replacing an element which could be a word, a group or a clause with a word in the next clause or sentence.

ix) Tunde: I want a plate of rice

Femi: I want one too

Ellipsis: This means deletion. The deletion of a syntactic element is often used to make room for grammatical cohesion in discourse.

x) Kunle: Has Kola washed the car?

Dipo: Yes, he has.

Lexical cohesion: This is achieved through reiteration of the same lexical word, its synonyms, its superordinate, its general term or collocation. For example:

xi) Same lexical word – We saw the man. The man was ugly.

xii) Synonym – I have a car. The automobile is old.

xiii) Superordinate or hyponym – I have a desktop in my room.

I work with the laptop.

xiv) Collocation – neither the father nor the mother spared the troublesome boy.

5.2 Coherence

Coherence and cohesion are like twin sisters (Sunday, 2004). Zradkovic (2017) says that for a text to be coherent, it has to be cohesive first. Cohesion and coherence are important aspect in Discourse Analysis. Modini (1982: 256) informs that while cohesion is about the connectivity within and between sentences, coherence is concerned with the connectedness of the contiguous linguistic strings. Brown and Yule (1985:224) reports that it is not always that coherence is explicit. Many a time, hearers have to do some filling based on their background knowledge or context.

According to Yule (2014), coherence is a factor which makes people to distinguish between connected texts that make sense from those which do not. It is a discourse analytic term used as a psychological phenomenon alluding to the fundamental development of proposition in terms of speech act. A coherent text, in the view of Simpson (1987) as seen in Adeoye (2014) is one considered to make sense in general level. Coherence refers to inference we make in

respect of covert propositional connections from an interpretation of the illocutionary act.

The exchange below illustrates this:

Speaker A: Please bring me a bottle of coke, I really need it.

Speaker B: I'm in the toilet.

Speaker A: OK

Apart from the fact that there is cohesion in this fragment of discourse, it is also coherent. It is coherent because Speaker A asked Speaker B for a favour, Speaker B's reply is a reason why he could not assist Speaker A. It can therefore be said that the key concept of coherence is not something which exists in the language, but something which exists in the people.

6. Textual Analysis and Discussions of Data

In the subsections below, the registers of medicine, religion and law are examined in terms of the single lexical terms found in cohesion and coherence.

6.1 Cohesion and Coherence in the Registers of Law, Medicine and Religion

De Beaugrande and Dressler (2002) define a text as "as a communicative occurrence which meets seven standards of textuality". The seven standards of textuality are cohesion, coherence, intentionality, acceptability, informativity, situationality and intertextuality. For any text to be realised as a semantic unit, it must possess textuality. A text is said to have textuality if it has unity with respect to its context. Both cohesion and coherence ensure the textuality of a text. Halliday and Hassan (1976:4) define cohesion thus: "it refers to the relations of meaning that exist within the text, and that define it as a text. Cohesion occurs where the interpretation of some element in the discourse is dependent on that of another. The one presupposes the other, in the sense that it cannot be effectively decoded except by recourse to it". Cohesion is achieved with both grammatical and lexical resources. The grammatical resources include reference, substitution, ellipsis and conjunction. The means of lexical cohesion are repetition, hyponymy and co-hyponymy, synonymy, antonymy, meronymy, converses and complementaries (Halliday and Hassan, 1976; Tanskanen, 2006).

These cohesive devices are pervasive in legal, medical and religious registers. The following example from the register of medicine broadly exemplifies some of the devices. Across the texts, the cohesive devices bring about textuality or connectivity in the texts in which they

appear. Through them, tracking and proper reference assignments are made possible, and these aid the decoding of such texts.

Example 1

Joel: You're an old hat at **this** already. I mean **you** had such an impassioned on Monday that was pretty incredible how impassioned **you** were. Did **you** practice that speech?

Answer: No, **I'm** upset. **I'm** upset. This is not, not **acting up**. **I'm** not **putting this up**, people are dying. Do **you** understand? **People** are dying. Like we just had news that **Herman Cain** died. **He** didn't have to die. **People** saying **he** shouldn't have worn a mask. Yes, **he** should have if he did haven't had hydroxychloroquine. But **she** should've worn a mask.

Joel: You're saying **Herman Cain** died, **he** just died. **He** didn't **need to**.

Answer: If someone would've given **him** hydroxychloroquine it's most likely **he** wouldn't have died. Just like every other **people**, just like every other **person** that has died from coronavirus did not have to.

Joel: But, **you** understand the **World Health Organisation**, the **FDA**, **they** don't agree with **you**?

Answer: Of course, **they** don't agree with **me**.(Dr Stella Emmanuel Interview with Joel Eisenbaim of KPRC Radio Station, Houston)

In this extract, the personal pronouns: 'you', 'I' and 'me' are variously deployed by the interviewer and the interviewee to refer to each other. They constitute instances of exophoric reference since they refer extratextually. They cannot be connected to any other item within the text. Apart from the instances of exophoric references, there are examples of demonstrative references signalled by the demonstrative pronoun: 'this' in 'You're an old hat at this already' and 'putting this up'. They both refer to the interviewee's vehement defence

of her stance on a medical matter. Since a central subject of discourse here is the death of ‘Herman Cain’ from COVID-19, all the instances of the singular third-person personal pronouns, ‘he’ and ‘him’, are anaphorically co-referential with ‘Herman Cain’. Also, ‘they’ as a plural third-person pronoun also refers to the names of two regulatory bodies in the domain of health, ‘WHO’ and ‘FDA’. These qualify as instances of nominal substitution and personal reference simultaneously. In addition, there is verbal ellipsis in ‘Yes, he should **have**[^] if he did haven’t had hydroxychloroquine’, ‘He didn’t **need to**[^]’ and ‘just like every other **person** that has died from Corona virus did not **have to**[^]’. Some verbal elements were removed in the positions marked with [^]. In the first sentence, it is the expression: ‘worn a mask’. In the second instance, the elided expression is ‘die’ and, in the third, it is ‘die’.

There are also some lexical markers of cohesion in the extract. There are instances of repetition, synonymy, hyponymy and co-hyponymy. There is the repletion of ‘dying’ and ‘died’ across the example. Additionally, both ‘acting up’ and ‘putting up’ are deployed as synonyms in ‘This is not, not acting up. I’m not putting this up, people are dying’. Also, ‘person’ and ‘people’ are used synonymously in ‘Just like every other people, just like every other person that has died from Corona virus did not have to’. Finally, there is hyponymy in ‘People are dying. Like we just had news that Herman Cain died’ where ‘Herman Cain’ is the hyponym and ‘People’ is the hypernym since ‘Herman Cain’ is an example of ‘people’ who are dying. Quite close to this is ‘World Health Organisation’ and ‘FDA’ in ‘But, you understand the World Health Organisation, the FDA, they don’t agree with you?’ Both are co-hyponyms of the superordinate term: regulatory bodies in medicine.

Example 2

You are worthy to be praise, **my redeemer**, **you** are worthy to be praised (7x). **Father almighty, the king of kings, the lord of lords, the ancient of days, the unchangeable changer, you** are worthy to be praised. **Father**, we thank **you** for **January**, we thank **you** for **February**, we thank **you** for **March**, we thank **you** for **April**, we thank **you** for **May**, we thank **you** for **June**. Now, we are thanking **you** for **July**. (Pastor Enoch Adeboye, “Perfect Blessing”)

This extract is from the opening part of a sermon. Precisely, it is from the prayer part. The first 'You' in the opening sentence refers to God. It is an example of exophoric reference. All other praise terms like 'my redeemer', 'Father almighty', 'the king of kings', 'the lord of lords', 'the ancient of days', 'the unchangeable changer' and 'father' are anaphorically connected to 'you' in the first sentence. In addition, all the titular terms are co-hyponyms of 'God's names. Similarly, the referenced names of months like 'January', 'February', 'March', 'April', 'May', 'June' and 'July' constitute a set of co-hyponyms under 'months of the year'.

Example 3

Sometime ago, a list of some Nigerians requested for the extradition of Mr Buruji Kashamu to the U.S. The U.S. presented a list of wanted Nigerians to the fourth **respondent** which is the NDLEA, and upon a look at **the list**, the name of **the applicant**, Buruji Kashamu was not on the list. So it is obvious that no request for the extradition of the **applicant** was made to the fourth **respondent**.

The Interpol interrogated the **applicant** and he was cleared by constituted **courts**. And it was proclaimed that the **petitioners** were unfair to the **applicant**. The **applicant** was also cleared by two **British courts**. **Nigerian courts** have also cleared **him** with two **judgments**. **They** have told the **NDLEA** to vacate his premises but **they** have not done **that**. So what do **they** want? (Channels TV Interview with Barrister Babaleye on the extradition of Senator Buruji Kasamu)

There are a number social actors mentioned in the extract above. One of them is 'Mr Buruji Kashamu'. In 'the extradition of the applicant', the term, 'applicant' is an example of nominal substitution; 'applicant replaces 'Buruji Kashamu'. Also, 'he' in 'he was cleared by constituted courts' and 'him' in 'Nigerian courts have also cleared him with two judgments'

are examples of personal reference and nominal substitution simultaneously. Also, there is a reference to ‘some Nigerians’ in ‘a list of some Nigerians requested for the extradition of Mr Buruji Kashamu to the US’. In another sentence, ‘And it was proclaimed that the petitioners were unfair to the applicant’, ‘petitioners’ is used in place of ‘some Nigerians’. This is an example of nominal substitution. One also finds related terms like ‘courts’, ‘British courts’ and ‘Nigerian courts’. Both ‘British courts’ and ‘Nigerian courts’ are co-hyponyms under the hypernym, ‘courts’. In addition, ‘they’ in ‘They have told the NDLEA to vacate his premises’, is another instance of nominal substitution as it replaces ‘British courts’ and ‘Nigerian courts’. There are also some references to ‘NDLEA’- National Drug Law Enforcement Agency. In ‘So it is obvious that no request for the extradition of the applicant was made to the fourth respondent’, ‘respondent’ refers to ‘NDLEA’. This is an example of nominal substitution too. Finally, in ‘They have told the NDLEA to vacate his premises but they have not done that’, ‘that’ is an instance of clausal substitution for the non-finite clause: ‘to vacate his premises’.

Coherence differs slightly from cohesion. “Cohesion refers to the grammatical and lexical elements on the surface of a text which can form connections between parts of the text” (Tanskanen 2006:7) and coherence is “conceptual dependencies in the textual world Coherence” (deBeaugrande and Dressler 2002:42). Coherence accounts for the conceptually-dependent connections in texts as against the overtly-marked markers which cohesion encompasses. The examples below show some instances of coherence in legalese, medical discourse and religious discourse. Aspects of coherence are often referred to as thought flow patterns in the literature. Some areas of coherence are cause and effect (condition-consequence, reason-result, means-purpose, means-result and grounds-conclusion), contiguity in time and space (chronological sequence, temporal overlap and bonding), associatives (simple contrast, simple comparison, statement and affirmation, statement and denial, concession-contradiction, contrastive alternation, supplementary alternation, paraphrase and amplification) (Osisanwo 2008: 40-43). Some of these are illustrated with examples below.

Example 4

Interviewer: To discuss the status of Ebola in Nigeria is the Deputy Incidence Manager of the Ebola Emergency Centre here in Lagos, Mr

Kayode Oguntimehin. Dr Oguntimehin, thank you for joining us on the News at 10.

Interviewee: Thanks for having me.

Interviewer: Well, lots of people are already scared that Ebola is in Nigeria, so tell us exactly what the status is.

Interviewee: Well, so far we have had 12 confirmed cases that stem from Mr Patrick Sawyer. But we are happy to announce that cases of new infections are fast falling and that is a good sign

Interviewer: Why is that? Is that because of the efforts by the EOC?

Interviewee: Well, yes. To date, we have had 894 contacts identified and monitored, about 18,500 face-to-face visits were conducted by contact tracers in order to be able to assess Ebola symptom development. We have also deployed a massive social mobilisation campaign. With new infections nearing zero and patients in isolation getting better, we are confident that our containment and treatment programme is working. (*93 Days*)

In this example from a televised interview with a medical expert during a public health crisis, there are a number of coherence indices. There are instances of cause and effect, associative, contiguity in time and space and elaboration. In the following sentences: 'Well, lots of people are already scared that Ebola is in Nigeria, so tell us exactly what the status is' and 'To date, we have had 894 contacts identified and monitored, about 18,500 face-to-face visits were conducted by contact tracers in order to be able to assess Ebola symptom development' there are two examples of cause and effect. In the first sentence, there is an example of ground-conclusion signalled by 'so'. In the second, the aspect of cause-effect found is means-purpose; it is indexed by 'in order to'. The only instance of associative found above expresses contrast and it is in 'Well, so far we have had 12 confirmed cases that stem from Mr. Patrick

Sawyer. But we are happy to announce that cases of new infections are fast falling and that is a good sign’ and it is marked by the coordinator, ‘but’.

The most pervasive coherence mode in the extract is bonding as an aspect of contiguity in time and space. Its marker is the coordinator, ‘and’, as found in sentences like ‘But we are happy to announce that cases of new infections are fast falling and that is a good sign’, ‘To date, we have had 894 contacts identified and monitored’ and ‘With new infections nearing zero and patients in isolation getting better, we are confident that our containment and treatment programme is working’. The last instance of coherence in the text is done through an aspect of clause complex called manner enhancement. The means used in achieving something is given. This is seen in ‘Well, yes. To date, we have had 894 contacts identified and monitored, about 18,500 face-to-face visits were conducted by contact tracers in order to be able to assess Ebola symptom development’ where ‘about 18,500 face-to-face visits were conducted by contact tracers in order to be able to assess Ebola symptom development’ states how the processes of contact identification and monitoring were undertaken.

Example 5

Pastor Bakare: Everything God created for the benefit of mankind is in abundance. Take for example, the fish that we eat almost on daily basis. If you have eaten fish in the past few days, lift up your hand (*congregation members raise their hands*). I can’t see your hands (*more congregation members raise their hands*). Ok, if you have been eating fish since you were born, lift up your hands. Fish! Eja osan, eja obokun, eja aro.... No human wants or needs, however huge or humongous can dent God’s account or deplete his resource base. That is the faith that builds the citadel. God’s resources are inexhaustible. Can you say that with me?

Congregation: (*in a loud chorus*) God’s resources are inexhaustible!

There are a number of cohesion and coherence devices in Example 12. Three prominent cohesive devices in the excerpt are repetition, homonymy, synonymy, anaphoric referencing and exophoric referencing. In the extract, there is the repetition of 'God', 'you' (to refer to the congregants), 'fish' and 'inexhaustible'. The term, 'fish', constitutes a superordinate term to such Yoruba expressions as 'eja osan', 'eja obokun' and 'eja aro'. They refer to types of fish. Hence, there is an instance of hyponymy in which the Yoruba expressions are the co-hyponyms. One also finds such instances of synonyms as 'want' and 'needs', 'huge and humongous' and 'account' and 'resource'. There is also the indexing of cohesion through anaphoric referencing. 'his' in 'his resource base' refers to 'God' in the opening sentence; 'that' in 'that is the faith' refers to the sentence which immediately precedes the one in which it occurs. In addition, both 'I' and 'you' are deployed as exophoric references to the cleric and his congregation.

Apart from the utilisation of cohesive devices, coherence terms are also used to achieve textuality in the extract above. The three coherence strategies found in the excerpt are statement affirmation, means-purpose and exemplification. The first sentence: 'Everything God created for the benefit of mankind is in abundance', is affirmed by the succeeding sentences. They illustrate and affirm the proposition that is a source of abundant gifts. In the first sentence, there is another instance of coherence called: means-purpose. 'Everything God created' denotes God's creation. The purpose of such is underscored by the phrase, 'for the benefit of mankind'. This indicates the purpose of such creations by God. Finally, the extract contains an instance of exemplification. The example is contained in sentences 2 to 7. They illustrate the limitlessness of God's provision for mankind which is asserted in the first sentence.

Example 6

The petitioners who participated in the election were aggrieved by the outcome and have approached the court vide their petition dated and filed on the 18th day of March praying the court by Paragraph 409 of the said petition as follows:

"409 WHEREFORE the petitioners prayed jointly and severally against the respondents as follows:

- a. That it may be determined that the 2nd Respondent was not duly elected by a majority of lawful votes cast in the said election and therefore the declaration and return of the 2nd Respondent by the 1st Respondent as the President of Nigeria is unlawful, undue, null, void and of no effect.

(Excerpts from the judgement of the supreme court of Nigeria on the 2019 presidential election between Former Vice- President, Alhaji Atiku Abubakar and the incumbent Nigerian leader, President Muhammadu Buhari).

This is a text from the legal register. It contains some examples of areas of coherence like contiguity in time and space, cause and effect and elaboration. The instances of contiguity in time and space fall into two subcategories – chronological sequence and bonding. Examples of chronological sequence in the excerpt are found in ‘The petitioners who participated in the election were aggrieved by the outcome and have approached the court vide their petition dated and filed on the 18th day of March praying the court by Paragraph 409 of the said petition’ and ‘therefore the declaration and return of the 2nd Respondent by the 1st Respondent as the President of Nigeria is unlawful, undue, null, void and of no effect’. The serialised actions following a chronological order in the first example are being aggrieved and approaching a court of law. Approaching a court of law appropriately also entails filing a petition and a petition must contain a prayer. The second has two nominalisations that encode sequential electoral processes. The first is declaring a winner and the second is returning a winner. There is also the example of bonding in ‘the petitioners prayed jointly and severally’. The petitioners simultaneously prayed to the court as a collective and as individuals.

There are also examples of cause and effect which encompasses means-purpose and grounds-conclusion. In ‘The petitioners... have approached the court vide their petition dated and filed on the 18th day of March praying the court by Paragraph 409 of the said petition’, there are two instances of means-purpose. The word, ‘vide’

suggests that the petition is a requisite means for the purpose of approaching the court. Also, the petition is a means for 'praying the court'. Grounds-conclusion as a coherence means is exemplified with 'That it may be determined that the 2nd Respondent was not duly elected by a majority of lawful votes cast in the said election and therefore the declaration and return of the 2nd Respondent by the 1st Respondent as the President of Nigeria is unlawful, undue, null, void and of no effect'. Here, 'therefore' indicates that 'the 2nd Respondent was not duly elected by a majority of lawful votes cast in the said election' is a ground for the conclusion that 'the declaration and return of the 2nd Respondent by the 1st Respondent as the President of Nigeria is unlawful, undue, null, void and of no effect'. The last coherence means found above is elaboration. The expressions in bold constitute an elaboration of the referenced petition in the opening paragraph. Even the expression, 'as follows', is an indication that what follows elaborates the petition by stating some parts of its contents.

7. Conclusion

Privileging on theoretical perspectives and concepts in Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG), this study has examined the relevance of Cohesion and Coherence to meaning encoding and decoding in the English Language. Having examined Cohesion and Coherence in the discourses of law, medicine and religion, the study foregrounds the centrality of these concepts to meaning-making in the mentioned fields. Cohesion occurs where the interpretation of some elements in a text is dependent on that of another; it is a linguistic means by which a text functions as a single unit while Coherence, is a linguistic factor which makes people to distinguish between connected texts that make sense from those which do not. The paper concludes that these linguistic concepts are so relevant to language to the extent that they help in analyzing the meaning of texts or discourses.

8. Recommendations

Language use in a particular field can be explicated in terms of cohesion devices, coherence means and other aspects of linguistic analysis. To enhance the professional competence of members of different communities of practice, efforts must be made to incorporate cohesion and coherence into the syllabi of professional courses at different educational levels. At the

tertiary level of education, departments should incorporate courses in the use of language in their fields into their syllabi. The contents of the courses should include cohesion and coherence. This can be extended to the postgraduate level. This should lay solid foundations for training professionally competent graduates. Also, English for Specific Purpose contents should be introduced into the curricular of examinations by professional bodies.

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